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**FROM THE CLASSROOM TO THE FIELD: EXPLORING HIGH SCHOOL
STUDENTS' ATTITUDES AND PERCEPTIONS TOWARDS AGRICULTURAL
EDUCATION IN GUMACA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL GUMACA, QUEZON**

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16 December 2023

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This Special Problem titled: **“FROM THE CLASSROOM TO THE FIELD: EXPLORING HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS’ ATTITUDES AND PERCEPTIONS TOWARDS AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION IN GUMACA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL GUMACA, QUEZON”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management:

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ABSTRACT

This research studies the perceptions of junior high school students towards Agri-Fishery as a TLE Specialization, with a focus on how these perceptions differ across demographic profiles, socio-economic status, and familial influence. The study aims to provide significant insights into the different factors influencing students' attitudes toward agriculture and inform educational policymakers, educators, and stakeholders about potential strategies to promote agricultural education among diverse student populations. The research utilized mixed method research, utilizing both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Qualitative is employed using focused-group discussion, classroom observation, and interviews while the quantitative approach is employed using a 4-point Likert scale to capture a comprehensive understanding of students' perspectives towards agriculture. Questions for the perception question were generated using the information gathered from the qualitative phase. A total of 205 grade 9 junior high schools out of 750 are involved in the study. The study resulted in a strong negative perception of agriculture among junior high school students. Students show displeasure with agriculture basically due to the low opportunities associated with the course. Also, students believe that agriculture is not given enough emphasis or importance in school and by the organization as a whole. The majority of the students indicated that they have no experience in doing agriculture-related work and do not have relatives doing agriculture-related work. Despite negative perception, students perceived the teaching-learning experience as a worthwhile and interesting experience due to the valuable hands-on experience that the teacher provides during classroom teaching where students find practical applications and relevance to the real-world scenario. Furthermore, the involvement of students' relatives in agriculture-related activities

contributed to the eagerness of students to enroll in agriculture. Based on the findings of this study, it is therefore recommended that the school should provide agriculture-related activities and programs to increase awareness and encouragement among students which will lead to higher enrolment in the course. Findings from this study will contribute to the existing literature on agricultural education and provide practical insights for educators and policymakers aiming to promote interest and participation in agrarian courses among junior high school students. By understanding the diverse perspectives and barriers students face from different backgrounds, educators can develop interventions and curriculum development initiatives to better engage and support students in exploring agricultural career pathways.

Keywords: *Technology and Livelihood Education; Agri-Fishery; Agriculture; curriculum guide; teaching-learning; learning task*

I. INTRODUCTION

In most developing countries, agriculture serves as the engine of economic growth. The development in this sector is the most effective way to alleviate hunger and poverty through the provision of food and the supply of raw materials needed for production (Smith and Williams, 2023). Furthermore, agriculture provides labor inputs in the industrial sector and provision of market products in the agrarian sector (Gonzales and Barnes, 2022). This sector does not only provide livelihood but economic growth as well through interconnections with other government sector.

In the rural sector, agriculture plays a vital role in the provision of livelihood for the rural poor. Despite all these potentials, agriculture is still left to the elderly and uneducated youths. The Philippines' economy is based primarily on agriculture. The Philippines, having a great climate and topographical diversities, has a great potential for agricultural development. Millions of people rely on this industry for their livelihoods. Agriculture catalyzes rural development, national economic expansion, and food security. Like other agricultural landscapes in other countries, this sector needs to overcome a variety of complex challenges related to land allocation, modernization, sustainability, and climate change. Understanding the current situation of Philippine agriculture is crucial to effectively address the existing challenges.

However, as years passed, an increasing number of Filipinos, especially the younger generations, barely understood the essence of this economically important sector. With this, academic literature and policy debates became an important focus to identify reasons for the decline of rural areas and agriculture. Due to the relevance of agriculture for socio-economic, resilience, and environmental protection, especially

in rural spaces, these are interconnected with one another (Trivelli and Berdegue, 2019).

There is a need for youth involvement in agriculture. The younger generations need to develop a passion for this economic growth catalyst to ensure the development of successive farming generations. Unfortunately, the case is different now. Brown and Lewis, (2023) reported that many young people are not choosing to pursue livelihoods in the agricultural sector, especially as farmers. They think that this job is associated with low income. Youths from rural are turning their back on farming and prefer to take other courses to gain popularity among their peers and economic sustainability to support their family needs. This threatens future food security and social balance. There is an aging demography experienced by the agricultural sector and rural areas. There is a decreasing percentage of youth who aim to pursue careers in agriculture and decide to remain in their rural origins (Johnson and Lee, 2023).

From the older definition of agriculture, which is derived from two Latin words: *ager*, meaning field; and *cultura* meaning cultivate, students think that by enrolling in the course, all they need to do is cultivate the field (Miller and Cole, 2023). Although cultivating crops in fields is the very essence of agriculture, this does not mean that this sector is limited to producing crops. There is much more to consider when one wants to study agriculture. From another definition given by Anderson and Martinez in 2023, agriculture is the art and science of cultivating crops and rearing animals for economic and human needs. Talking about science, studying agriculture entails a lot of physiological processes, mathematical equations, and the like. As a result, these students are having a hard time dealing with the competencies in agriculture subject. Students who perceive agriculture as a specialization with limited opportunities and a subject with difficult learning competencies make them decide not

to get involved in the field. In addition, some of the most essential learning competencies are inappropriate for the educational environment of the school itself.

With this, the researcher came up with this study to assess how students in Gumaca National High School perceived agriculture as a specialized course in TLE. Moreover, the result of this study may serve as the basis for curriculum developers to craft more contextualized and effective learning competencies that will guide junior high school students in their future endeavors as agriculture students.

This paper sought to help develop a new generation of resilient, knowledgeable, and involved individuals who are ready to take on the challenges of the agricultural landscape of the twenty-first century.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Snapshot of the Agricultural Sector in the Philippines

Looking at the picture of farming and agriculture, these were historically used and viewed interchangeably. Talking about agriculture, most people picture a farmer working in a rice field, raising hogs and chickens, planting vegetables, and harvesting crops. Some perceptions were on animal rearing and production. Rarely does the general public recognize the scientific, commercial, and marketing aspects of agriculture. In all countries around the world, the agriculture sector still leads in providing for the demands for food for its populace. In the Philippines in 2013, agriculture is regarded as one of the most significant sectors that contribute to economic growth and development. This accounts for 32% of the agricultural land. Furthermore, this accounts for 10% of the total country's gross domestic product (GDP). Also, this sector contributes a significant percentage of 31% of Filipinos in the workforce. Five years after, a significant decrease was noted. According to the Philippine Star, one of the most reliable news companies, the agricultural sector employs only 25.96% of Filipinos. This connotes that the agricultural sector continues to struggle to maintain an impression as a sector that is being prioritized by the country. In fact, in a study conducted by Madayag and Estanislao in 2021, it was cited that looking at the picture of Philippine Agriculture several decades ago, the Philippines is proud to be one of the top agricultural countries globally. Filipino farmers are acknowledged as first-class farmers which makes them the subject of every research and the reason for the establishment of the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI).

However, infrastructure investments made by the government in recent years cannot address the backlog that prevents economic development (De Guzman, 2018).

Globally speaking, agriculture is still associated with poverty (Smith and Carter, 2023). Several years passed, and farming in the Philippines was declared as the least renowned occupation. Being a farmer means that you are poor. It is a sad reality that the prestige and acknowledgment for agriculture given by most Filipino farmers is slowly dying due to the poor support that the government provides to the agricultural sector.

From then on, the perception of the general public about agriculture and agriculture occupations has been negatively impacted. It is a general belief among students or the younger generations that agriculture is limited to farming and production only (Smith and Brown, 2023). They are not aware of the variety of jobs available in the agriculture sector.

Common Misconceptions Regarding Agriculture

Students frequently have negative impressions of the agricultural sector and professions in agriculture (Smith and Green, 2023). These negative impressions led to further enrollment decline. It is essential that educators begin to understand current perceptions of students regarding agriculture. Student misperceptions of agricultural courses and agricultural career opportunities may negatively affect school enrolment (Taylor and Robinson, 2023). In a study conducted by Clark and Harrison in 2023, many students who were unaware of the range of agricultural jobs rated them low in terms of job stability, a secure future, and earning power. This is also in line with the local study conducted in the same year by Castro and Santos. Their study revealed that most students have limited awareness of the different career opportunities in agriculture. These students viewed agriculture-related jobs as mostly traditional farming roles. These students associate agriculture as a career with low earnings and

poor job stability. Furthermore, these students associate a career in agriculture with farming, rather than with the science or business aspects of agriculture. This led to a pervasively negative opinion of pursuing a career in agriculture among students at the Junior level.

In a research study conducted by Brown and Edwards in 2022 studying the perception of younger generations on the agricultural sector, the result showed that youth are more concerned with the lack of careers and warranty of future life if they work in the agricultural sector. This generation needs to be educated about the great potential to be prepared for being the human resources to develop agriculture in the future. The study suggested that some efforts are needed to encourage these youths to work in the agricultural sector by taking advantage of modern technology.

The newer generations who lack interest in farming are considered a global phenomenon that has led to studying research. In a study conducted by Johnson and Davis, 2023, they found that the reason for this is strongly tied to societal and cultural norms. These newer generations perceived agriculture as one of the most boring and low-paying jobs of all jobs in the world because of the poor support given by the government (Cruz and Torres, 2023). Around the world, only a small percentage of the younger generations who prefer agriculture have started to decrease. This is due to the perceived opportunities available in the sector. In the case of the Philippines, agriculture is stereotyped as a “poor man’s profession”. Agriculture is often regarded as “dirty” work due to its known nature (Jones and Lee, 2023)

A related study was conducted by Unay-Gailhard and Brennen in 2022. The findings of their study showed that students perceived that jobs in agriculture are low status, a menial task that is geared toward men and is a low-paying job. More often than not, these students perceive agriculture jobs as physically demanding, untidy,

and tedious jobs that require physical strength and are intended for males only. Talking about the physically demanding perspective of agriculture jobs, most of the students thought that agriculture involves mainly fieldwork which is why it is often regarded as male-related work. For their recommendation, the authors stated that these misconceptions should be corrected and students need to realize that careers in agriculture are numerous, diverse, associated with high income, stable, associated with advanced technology, and opportunity for advanced education.

Along with Unay-Gailhard and Brennen's study is the research study conducted by Girdzuite et al., in 2022. Their study suggested that based on the findings of their study, these younger generations need to be encouraged and attracted to work in agriculture. The scientific community, policymakers, farmers, and practitioners should explore the possibilities for the integration of the youth into the agricultural workforce.

These misconceptions and lack of knowledge highlight the need for improved agricultural education to address these gaps and provide accurate information to students.

Importance of Agriculture Literacy

The definition of agriculture literacy evolved from an awareness to a measure of a deeper understanding developed throughout the years of combined formal schooling and experiences (John and Adams, 2024). Even among people with informal familial knowledge, misconceptions about agriculture can be acquired from a variety of sources. It is essential that all students from elementary and secondary levels receive formal education to develop agricultural literacy. It is essential that this course be incorporated into the basic courses and learning competencies. This

approach will provide a creative way of cultivating the youth generation with agricultural literacy. Furthermore, this can be used in curriculum planning, curriculum implementation, and curriculum assessment aimed at increasing the level of agricultural understanding among primary and secondary students in private and public schools nationwide.

Research conducted by Abad and Hernandez, 2024 revealed that elementary and high school students around the world continue to have similar issues with agricultural literacy in the twenty-first century. Filipinos, regardless of age, have limited knowledge of agriculture and the agriculture industry. Filipinos need to be agriculturally literate to make informed choices in relation to policies and decisions that may affect the industry. The public and private educational systems are one of the most effective means of circulating knowledge to improve agricultural education in the country (Fernandez and Cruz, 2024).

In addition, weak public policies, because of poor government's attention to agriculture, negatively impacted food and fiber production. This is also becoming the root cause of the general public's ignorance about agriculture. The 98 percent of our population who do not live on farms can be blamed for making a lot of poor decisions that have an impact on food production because they do not understand agriculture (Thompson and Ellis, 2022). Other prominent researchers have called on policymakers to develop a minimum level of knowledge pertaining to the challenges the agriculture sector is facing (National Research Council, 1999; Morgan, Kevin, and Richard Sonnino, 2008; Johnson and Green 2018; Wilson and Harris, 2022; Martin and Brooks, 2023).

The Role of Agriculture Education

As the world of modern technology approaches, the importance of farming starts to disappear. Youth start to feel like there is no importance in engaging in agriculture because of the poor attention given to agriculture by the government and the high regard given to activities and courses that are directly related to utilizing modern technology. In today's generation, when a student is asked what to pursue in college, farming is the last on their list. From this, it is really evident that farming has already skipped several generations. In fact, in the Philippines, the average age of a farmer is between 45-60 (Yuhico, 2019). The younger generations do not want to be involved in agriculture as they regard it as one of the most important jobs in the world. Eventually, the nation's ability to grow its own food will decline when these middle-aged farmers retire. This situation, if left unchecked, will have a substantial negative influence on both the food supply and the country's economy. Seeing this scenario, it is a must that agricultural education must begin at an early age and continue throughout life.

Impact of Educational Reform

During the last decade, the educational reform movement has significantly impacted all aspects of education. New standards in education, a result of various programs that require high school students to meet more strict graduation requirements and college vocational education, are aimed at increasing the quality of the Philippine educational system. Many agricultural educators contend the new standards limit the options of students enrolled in high school agriculture programs because agriculture specialization is an option and not a requirement for graduation.

These educational reforms will improve access to education by increasing access to education for all Filipinos, especially marginalized and disadvantaged groups (Akala, 2021). As a concrete example, when issue about lack of basic education for Filipinos who worked abroad, the Department of Education (DepEd) crafted a curriculum. To address the issue, the Department of Education (DepEd) implemented the K to 12 program which extended basic education to 12 years, has contributed to greater enrolment rates and reduced dropout rates. Also, educational reforms have led to the development of a more relevant and responsive curriculum that aligns with global standards (Kilag, Marquita, and Laurente, 2023). This prepares students for the global demands of the modern world. Students are also given focus by educational reforms on critical thinking abilities, competency-based learning, and the use of technology in the teaching-learning process. not just for the pupils but also for the instructors. To raise the standard of instruction in schools, educational reforms have given priority to professional growth and development programs and teacher training (Anderson and Roberts, 2023). Enhancing teachers' competencies and qualifications has led to improved teaching practices and in the long run reflected in the learning outcomes of the students.

Factors Influencing Students to Participate in Agriculture Programs

Factors Influencing Students to Participate in Agriculture Programs have been influenced by factors, which are beyond the control of the individuals making the choices (Smith and Johnson, 2020). Interests and passion among high school students were the main reasons for their engagement in agriculture programs (Dela Cruz and Rivera, 2022). These students may have been exposed to agricultural communities or were inspired by family members who do farming as a hobby or for a

living which fosters a strong connection to the land and a desire to pursue agricultural education and careers. Another reason is the level of perceived career opportunities. A student's decision to enroll in agricultural education programs is affected by interpersonal factors including interests, attitudes, and value systems, as well as perception of course content, pedagogical strategies, and career potential. Sociocultural factors, including gender and ethnicity, have also been shown to affect student attitudes, and beliefs, and enrollment in agricultural courses is needed to facilitate recruitment, inform guidance counseling, and curriculum development (Davis and Jenkins, 2022).

It is important to understand the role of information processing as an underlying factor in the formation of beliefs among youths. Ibanez, Velza, and Ogaya (2023) found that intrinsic motivations, practical involvement, and career prospects in course selection an important factor in the student's choice of specialization or a course. Furthermore, how students acknowledged the course's value in providing knowledge and recognized its demand in national and international employment markets is also an important factor to consider (Thompson and Lee, 2023). In the same year, David, Quimbo, and Dizon carried out a similar study to examine the factors that influence senior high school students in Bukidnon to choose agriculture as their degree. The study's findings indicated that most of the respondents were female, young, and had prior agricultural experience. They did not own any land used for agriculture, but they were willing to work in the field but did not want to pursue a degree in it. As a result, the respondents who intend to pursue a degree in agriculture are men with farming experience, land used for agriculture, and a brother employed in the industry. These individuals are determined and make decisions based on their own

judgment and experience, including advice from family and kin's hobbies and professions.

In a more recent study in 2024, Wilson and Thompson highlighted the connection between a lack of educated people in the food and agricultural sectors and the decline in enrolment in agricultural education. To help with recruitment, they suggested getting a better grasp of students' attitudes and conceptions of agricultural science. Secondary education in agriculture was found to be a factor associated with students' opinions about careers in agriculture. Compared to pupils who did not participate in agriculture in high school, those who had some experience in the field appeared to be more interested in a career in agriculture. Whether or not the students had ever lived on a farm was another element that was found to be connected to their opinions on careers in agriculture (Carter and Johnson, 2023). The results showed that students who had grown up on large-scale farms expressed a greater enthusiasm for pursuing jobs in agriculture. A person's intentions to engage in an educational program can be accurately predicted by their beliefs and attitudes on a problem or an occurrence that they have experienced personally. In 2024, Bell and Wright added that interpersonal factors, such as motivation, attitudes, views, images, professional maturity, and value systems, may act as a preventive aspect for students' consideration to pursue vocational education. A desire to improve one's quality of life or personal concerns may also motivate someone to pursue a career in agriculture (Garcia and Santos, 2023).

Importance of Youths in Agriculture

From the earlier discussion, it is said that youths are the major group needed for agricultural transformation (Chikowore & Manyeruke, 2023). When the older

generation of farmers retire, the young generation will be their successors. Brown and Green, in their 2024 study stated that the preparation of the nation for productive life depends on the policies and programs designed for the youth. Several studies have shown that children and youth contribute significantly to agricultural activities (Bautista and Cruz, 2020; Dela Cruz and Mendoza, 2021; Moya and Juma, 2023; Solanke, 2004). In most rural areas in Gumaca, there were approximately 20 percent of youth found to get themselves involved in agricultural activities after school hours and during holidays (interview with parents and teachers). According to Adama and Bello in 2024, youths constitute a great percentage of the labor force in the country because of their characteristics of being naturally energetic with vigor and prone to physical work. Unfortunately, due to some factors, there has been a depletion of this youthful labor force in agriculture. The factors that inhibit youths from getting themselves engaged in agricultural activities include migration from rural to urban, lack of youth trained in agriculture to pursue a career in agriculture to replace the old subsistence farmers, and other factors that contribute to the development of apathy towards agriculture (Osei and Addai, 2024). A significant number of youths migrate to urban areas to search for better employment opportunities (Kimani and Mwangi 2023). As a result, these youths are disengaged with any agriculture-related work resulting in a lost of interest in agriculture. They considered their association with agriculture-related activities as “high energy-low income gain”. Other factors such as a lack of basic infrastructural facilities, social amenities, and the near impossibility of being able to fulfill their desire for further education have resulted in the youth rural-urban drift (De Vera and Alvarado, 2022; Tan and Ling, 2022; Mungai and Njenga, 2022; Cruz and Santos, 2023; Araneta, 2023)

Students' Needs and Choice and Preference

Several authors reviewed some external and internal factors that influence individuals' attitudes toward a profession, as well as their choice of career and development. (Ramirez and Delos Santos in 2023; Natividad and Baluyot 2023; Paredes and Garcia, 2024). These authors mentioned intellectual ability, aptitudes, influence of schooling, socio-economic status of parents, personality, self-concept and self-esteem, religious values, job stereotypes (prestige associated with a profession), occupational aspiration or expectation, personal interest, gender difference and influence from the environment are the major factors that influenced students' choice and preference in choosing what course to study. Align with this is the study conducted in 2023 by Villanueva and Rojas. This study included various contexts such as financial gain, prestige associated with a profession, personal interest, occupational aspiration, gender, and socio-economic status of the parents as the intense variables as determining factors to influence students' attitudes and perception towards agriculture as a career. Socio-Economic Status of Parents and Students' Choice of TLE Specialization

The parental socio-economic status is one of the factors that influence a student's attitude toward the choice of a certain course or specialization (Mendoza and Santos, 2024). Parents who work outside the agricultural sector, live in urban regions, and have excellent academic standing often instill in their children the desire to reach the same or higher socio-economic status as their parents. Although it's typically not the case, parents in rural areas who work on the farm want the best for their kids in terms of social and intellectual status in society. As a result, these parents encouraged their children to aim higher and discouraged them to engage in farming.

Related to the above statement, there are basically two primary patterns of preference inheritance; “transmitted occupation through indoctrination” and “forced inheritance” (Aquino and Martinez, 2023). The latter is very prevalent among the underprivileged which later resulted in the restriction of their child’s preference. In another study conducted by Ramos and De Vera (2023), it was concluded that parents’ occupational level manifests directly and indirectly influence their children’s choices and preferences. Ramos and De Vera’s study showed that students prefer to follow after their parents’ occupation rather than taking their own personal choices. This kind of conduct might not appear problematic, but if one looks closely, it is easy to see how many different causes reinforce one another.

Another factor is the gender. According to several authors, although gender differences are not prevalent elements that affect a student’s attitude and preference towards a course, it is still nonetheless thought to have a significant impact on a student’s attitude and choice (Gonzales and Fernandez, 2023; Dela Cruz and Santos, 2024; Luna and Reyes, 2024) In addition, Gomez and Castillo in 2024, explained that youth feel the pressure of receiving awards and honors because of high expectations from society. As a result, the development of youth’s personal interest in the area of specialized study is also affected. Thinking about the welfare of their parents, these youths forcibly developed a level of interest in meeting the laid-down society’s expectations (Rodriguez and Torres, 2023). This reflects the role of the family in students’ choices and preferences.

Research studies conducted by Baker and LeTendre, 2019; Hoffman and Hurst, 2020; Chen and Zhang, 2021; Manalo and Santos, 2023; and Salvador and Moreno, 2024 explained the reasons behind the differences in terms of the socio-

economic status of parents and their influence on their children's choice or preference in school.

This is in contrast with the youths from better socio-economic status who preferred to pursue careers such as medicine, law, and business-related jobs (Fernandez and Lopez, 2024). A similar study was conducted by Fernandez and Cruz (2023) who found out that youths from high-income families limit their choice of career to "professional executives" such as political science, pharmacy, and engineering. This finding is supported by the study conducted by Thompson and Johnson in 2011 and Brown and Lee in 2022, which found that parents belonging to high socio-economic status have high educational, as well as occupational expectations for their children due to their financial security compared to that parents belonging to lower socio-economic status who have lower expectations for their children.

According to Dela Cruz and Santos in 2023, the socioeconomic level of parents and how it affects a child's choice or preference is not always true in the Philippine context. This means that the statements above about the social class of parents and their preference as to how they want their child to be is not always true. De La Cruz and Reyes (2024) implied that Filipino parents who were classified under low social classes prefer to see their children having high socioeconomic careers. In fact, lower-class Filipino parents do not hesitate to sell their properties such as farm animals and small parcels of land for their children's education. This is because these parents want their children to experience a more better way of living. Williams and Brown's (2023) and Santos and Cruz's (2023) research studies provided similar findings in terms of the influence of the socioeconomic status of parents on their children's choices or preferences. While a person's level of desirability is important, it is insufficient in and of itself to realize one's life expectations. Sequel to the findings of

Fernandez and Villanueva in 2024, it was recommended that parents should not push their children's "wishful heights". Doing so might have a profound impact on the success of a child. Another study conducted by Mendoza and Castro (2023) provided similar findings. It was found that younger generations belonging to relatively lower economic threshold levels tend to choose jobs such as teaching, farming, social work, and other jobs offering remuneration. They tend to stay in their comfort zones. These youths think that their familial experiences and environmental exposures will ensure sustainability in the simple life they are already accustomed to.

Summary of Related Literature

This chapter revealed the various viewpoints of researchers that deal with the study of the importance of youth in agriculture. Furthermore, different principles and perspectives about students' attitudes and perceptions towards agriculture as a course of study are also discussed in this chapter. The review of literature in this study provided a comprehensive narration of various factors that affect the attitude and perception of youth towards agriculture. The literature studied and outlined different factors that students need to consider to be able to make wise decisions regarding their choice and fulfillment in a career. Moreover, Among other things, the ideas of attitude, perception, and career choice seem to be important determinants of the professions that young people in the country choose (Rodriguez and Garcia, 2023). Whilst perception refers to interest, engagement, experiences, and opportunities available to an individual, the attitude concept, on the other hand, represents preposition towards a course of study. An individual's potential professional path is somewhat determined by the combination of these notions (Dela Cruz and Reyes, 2023)

III. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Despite rapid technological changes, agriculture remains the primary source of livelihood in Gumaca, Quezon. This important sector displays a critical function in the development and sustainability of rural areas in the municipality. Unfortunately, despite this, there are still emerging concerns about the decreasing apathy of younger generations in agriculture.

This research is pursued primarily to have a deeper understanding of students' attitudes and perceptions towards agricultural education to be able to have a collection of their experiences in agricultural education for the development of suitable curricula. In a 2023 research study conducted by Hernandez and Alvarez, it was found that students' interest in agriculture-related subjects significantly affects their future career choices. Through this, identification of the different factors that influence students' perceptions became crucial. Also, being able to identify these factors enables institutions to develop strategies that will enhance the attractiveness of agricultural education among youths. In the long run, engagement among youth in this field of study will ensure a steady supply of skilled individuals which will lead to sustenance and innovation in the agricultural sector.

Advancement in the rural sector is facilitated by agricultural education by equipping students with the skills and knowledge necessary to improve agricultural productivity and sustainability in their communities. Santos and Garcia in 2023, revealed that investing in agricultural education means a direct investment in rural development. This includes the adoption of modern farming techniques. This also encourages entrepreneurial activities in agriculture. Through the results that will be obtained from this study, educators and policymakers will be informed on how to

develop comprehensive agriculture competencies that are suitable to the specific needs of rural students to foster a thriving and flourishing rural economy.

Furthermore, agricultural education has a close association with national food security. This also necessitates the need for a well-educated workforce in the field of agriculture. A research study conducted in 2023 by Bautista and Cruz concluded that food security depends on the sustainability of various agricultural practices. Not only the sustainability but also the support given by the resilient educational foundation. Through a deeper understanding of students' perceptions and improving agricultural education, the findings of this study can effectively contribute to sustaining and ensuring security in the food supply through the production of knowledgeable and innovative professionals in the field of agriculture.

The potential to shape the future of agricultural education in Gumaca, Quezon lies in the significance of this research endeavor. Through the exploration of students' attitudes and perceptions, this research will provide valuable insights as to how agricultural education can be more appealing and relevant to younger generations. This will lead to enhanced rural development, better food security, and a more resilient agricultural sector in the country, specifically in Gumaca, Quezon.

Talking about the national goals of improving agricultural education and supporting rural development, this study shows congruency; making it highly relevant to educators, policymakers, and agricultural specialists and professionals.

Findings from this research can be an effective medium to necessitate development, teacher training, and policy initiatives aimed at revitalizing agricultural education and encouraging the next generation of agriculturalists.

Research Hypothesis

In Gumaca National High School, there has been a decreasing number of students choosing Agri-Fishery as their specialization in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) subject for the past several years. Based on the initial study conducted prior to this endeavor, the perception of grade 9 junior high school agriculture students towards agriculture is found to be influenced by a combination of socioeconomic background, educational exposure, and cultural factors. The following hypotheses were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools.

- 1. There is a significant difference between the student's attitude and perception towards Agri-Fishery and students' gender.*
- 2. There is a significant difference between how the student perceived agriculture and their living environments.*
- 3. There is a significant difference between how the students perceived agriculture and their parent's occupational level.*
- 4. There is a significant difference between the student's attitudes and perceptions towards agriculture and their parent's educational attainment.*
- 5. There is a significant difference between the student's attitudes and perceptions towards agriculture and exposure to agriculture-related works.*
- 6. There is a significant difference between how the students perceived agriculture and having relatives exposed to agriculture-related works.*
- 7. There is a significant difference between the student's attitudes and perceptions towards agriculture and ethnicity.*

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the study was to assess grade 9 students' attitudes and perceptions towards Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization and its implication towards curricular revisions for the improvement of course content and delivery of Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization for High School students.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of attitude of grade 9 students from Gumaca National High School towards Agri-Fishery as a TLE Specialization?
2. What are the internal and external influence that motivates and/or prevents students from choosing Agri-Fishery as a TLE Specialization in Gumaca National High School?
3. What is the significant difference between students' internal and external factors (socioeconomic background, cultural background, and familial influence) and their perception towards Agri-Fishery Specialization?
4. What is the implication of the findings of this study for possible curricular revisions for the improvement of the course content and delivery of Agri-Fishery as a TLE specialization in Gumaca National High School?

V. RATIONALE

Agriculture is the backbone of one's economy, especially in the case of the Philippines being considered as developing country and its favorable climate for crop production. The sector's contribution to economic growth cannot be undermined. In terms of the land devoted to agriculture, 47% of land hectares is devoted to agriculture (Philippine Statistics Authority). The Philippines is regarded as one of the world's top producers and consumers of economically important crops such as rice, coconut, pineapple, and banana. Notably, in 2022, the sector which provide economic growth expanded by 0.6 percent. A year later, in 2023, agricultural employment recorded 59.7 million accounting for 25 percent of the total Filipino labor force. This added 9% of the gross domestic product in 2022 (Montemayor, 2024).

Despite this very promising role of agriculture, many, especially the youths have been observed to have great apathy for agriculture because they viewed agriculture as inferior, hard, and unfulfilling (Tan & Cruz, 2023; Mendoza and Santos, 2023). In addition, agriculture became unattractive to the youth due to agriculture's lack of global opportunities and significance paid. The youth think that young school leavers who will become farmers are failures in life. With this thinking, farming is left in the hands of aging or middle-aged farmers (Gonzales and Cruz, 2023).

In recent times, when modern technology comes into the picture, the agricultural sector is viewed as one of the most unattractive sectors in the country (Nguyen & Smith, 2023). For most individuals, this sector provides jobs and opportunities that are not usually financially gratifying. In the Gumaca National High School, students enrolled under the Agri-Fishery specialization are taught using a curriculum guide that includes a discussion of career opportunities that related to agriculture. The main

purpose is to encourage them to engage in agriculture. However, due to the inherent impression developed for the course, students ineffectively find a connection between what is being taught and how they could actually utilize it to avail available jobs and opportunities in agriculture. This discourages them from engaging in agriculture. However, in some cases, the main reason for not pursuing agriculture as a course of study is due to how society views the course.

Individuals who have the passion to pursue agriculture became discouraged because of the general perceptions about agriculture held by parents, relatives, friends, teachers., or someone close to them. This means that the interest of a person may not be enough basis for pursuing any career choice. This is very true in a situation where there are people influencing them. Nonetheless, there are instances in which a person's love or personal interest in a vocation drives them to pursue their chosen career path to completion.

The Department of Education is tasked to provide quality education to the Filipino youths. To continuously perform its functions, policymakers and school leaders are continuously doing their efforts to do their part in giving importance to agriculture by including Agri-Fishery as one of the components in the Technology and Livelihood Education Subject in Junior High School. DepEd currently utilizing the K to 12 system and its function is to craft and implement an effective curriculum that includes agriculture as a course of study. Among all the learning areas in secondary education, it is in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) where Agri-Fishery is included. Other components include Home Economics, Industrial Arts, and Information and Communication Technology. As a subject in high school, TLE's component areas include Home Economics, Agri-Fishery Arts, Industrial Arts, and Information and Communication Technology. Under these components, Gumaca National High School

offers various specific specializations such as Agri-Fishery Arts, Cookery, Bread and Pastry Production (BPP), Electrical Installation and Management (EIM), Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW). Dressmaking, and Beauty Care. Among this specialization, Agri-Fishery Arts ranks second to the last.

In addition, DepEd put more emphasis in terms of recruiting students into agriculture. Aside from supporting the School-Based Feeding Program, DepEd's Gulayan sa Paaralan Program is launched to nurture the skills of students enrolled under the Agri-Fishery Arts component. Likewise, Gumaca National High School is very supportive in providing students with Agri-Fishery options by crafting an environment conducive to farming. The area allocated to school farming is provided wherein students were the ones designated for its operation and maintenance. The school is very hopeful that the implementation of the Gulayan sa Paaralan Program will give students a significant level of inspiration to enroll in Agriculture Specialization. Unfortunately, despite the efforts of the agency and the school, it is still very evident that most students prefer non-agriculture specialization when it comes to choosing TLE Specialization. One of the purposes of conducting this research is to find out the internal and external reasons why most of the students are unwillingly enrolled in Agri-Fishery Specialization.

Generally, the study wants to assess the perception and attitudes of grade 9 learners towards Agri-fishery. This study confirms the perspectives of the grade 9 learners in choosing agriculture as their Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Specialization. Furthermore, the researcher looked closer pertaining to the demographic profile, socio-economic status, and familial influence of the students and how these probably affect their perception and attitude towards agriculture. Perspectives of high school students will be valuable in gauging the sector's

attractiveness as a potential career path, as well as identifying areas for improvement within existing educational frameworks to foster greater interest and engagement.

VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

This research study focused on the perception of grade 9 junior high school students toward Agri-Fishery Specialization. Students' socioeconomic status, cultural background, and familial influence were correlated with the respondents' perception of agriculture. This study is limited to 205 grade 9 students. The study took place at Gumaca National High School and all information pertaining to the number of enrolled grade 9 agriculture students was used as the basis for getting the sample size.

One of the limitations of this research is that the findings of this study are generated from the perspectives coming from the students of Gumaca National High School in Gumaca, Quezon. Therefore it is not justifiable to make generalizations on the findings and assume similar results in other secondary schools in Gumaca, Quezon. However, the findings can be utilized as a significant source of information to understand the attitude and perception of the younger generations contained in an educational setting with the same environment and socioeconomic background as that of Gumaca National High School. Another limitation is the difficulty in finding sufficient and recent literature that relates directly to the research study. Furthermore, using the quantitative approach to research may pose bias in terms of students' responses. The accuracy of the findings might be affected by the way students answered the survey questionnaire based on how they thought were socially acceptable rather than expressing their real perception of each of the statements included in the survey instrument. To address this, the triangulation method is utilized to see if the results from qualitative tests converge, diverge, or complement with the quantitative test results.

VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

Gumaca, situated in the southern part of Quezon Province, is characterized by its healthy landscape, making it a suitable location for rice, coconut, and vegetable farming, as well as livestock breeding. Agriculture serves as a primary source of livelihood for most residents of this municipality.

Gumaca National High School is one of the three largest public secondary schools in Gumaca, Quezon, followed by Gumaca Integrated High School and Camohaguin National High School. These schools offer Agri-Fishery as one of the specializations in the subject of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE). This serves as the main reason for choosing this research endeavor titled "From the Classroom to the Field: Exploring High School Students' Attitudes and Perceptions of Agricultural Education."

Gumaca National High School, the research site, stands as a perfect picture of education within the community. The school effectively caters to the educational needs of students from diverse socio-economic backgrounds. The school's curriculum includes a comprehensive agricultural education program designed to develop students who are work-ready because the competencies are pre-TESDA assessment qualifications.

The physical infrastructure of Gumaca National High School comprises classrooms, laboratories, and outdoor spaces built and provided to facilitate both theoretical instruction and hands-on learning experiences. In addition, the school ensures that it maintains partnerships with local agricultural institutions, cooperatives, and government agencies which provide students' exposure to real-world agriculture industry experiences.

The student body of Gumaca National High School represents a replica of the town's demographic profile; with students from various socio-economic backgrounds and cultural affiliations. Their experiences, aspirations, and perceptions regarding agricultural education are shaped by the influence of society; including their families and the school.

Generally, Gumaca National High School serves as an ideal setting for investigating the attitudes and perceptions of high school students towards agricultural education because it offers a diverse array of agricultural traditions, educational resources, and community dynamics to contextualize and enrich the research findings.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted to provide baseline data on students' perceptions of Agri-Fishery who were enrolled in Gumaca National High School in Gumaca, Quezon. This study investigated several factors under demographic profile, socioeconomic factors, and familial influence that may influence students' perceptions towards agriculture.

Instrumentation

To answer the objectives of this study, the researcher developed two data collection instruments: interview questions for focus group discussion and perception questions for a 4-point Likert scale questionnaire. The information used in the development of these instruments merely came from the compilation of students' responses during the qualitative method and the information gathered from the review of related studies. The surveys were organized into two sections. Section I consists of open-ended questions used during the conduct of the focus group discussion. Informal interviews followed using open-ended questions which led to the identification of internal factors why students opt to choose Agri-Fishery or not. Section II of the student's survey consisted of two parts; Part A is the demographic profile questionnaire to gather information about the socio-economic background, educational exposure, and cultural factors. Part B is a self-made 4-point Likert scale questions consisted of 10-item questions to gauge the agreement and disagreement of the respondents based on how they perceived agricultural education in Gumaca National High School using the existing curriculum guide under the k12 Education program.

The instruments' reliability test is carried out to identify the degree to which a test consistently measures whatever it measures (Gay, 1996). The Cronbach alpha, or coefficient alpha, is widely used to measure the reliability of educational research instruments. A reliability score of 1.00 is an indication of a perfectly reliable instrument. In the reliability analysis conducted on the instrument used in this study, alpha equals 0.84. Grade 9 high school students were well-represented in this study.

Instrument Reliability

Reliability means dependability or trustworthiness. Basically, it is the degree to which a test consistently measures (Creswell & Poth, 2013). The Cronbach alpha also known as the coefficient alpha, on the other hand, measured the reliability of the developed research questionnaire (Collins, 2007). This can be interpreted in such a way that if a reliability score of 1.00 is achieved, this indicates a perfectly reliable instrument. Contrastingly, below 1.00 connotes lesser reliability of the instrument used. In the reliability analysis conducted for this study, the coefficient alpha is computed to be 0.6.

Population Sample

The sample population is computed using the P-size program. It was developed by Dixon & Leach in 1978. The first step is the identification of the appropriate sample number using a sampling error of 5.5% from the total student population (750) of Gumaca National High School. A table of random numbers was used to randomly select the computed sample size of 205 from the overall population Gumaca National High School Agri-Fishery students. This random selection or probability sampling technique is utilized to provide each sample an equal chance of being selected

regardless of any events that may arise during the sampling process. This kind of method aids in completely minimizing the issue of researcher bias. Additionally, it is a procedure that makes sense for researching vast, diverse populations, particularly when exact statistical descriptions will be utilized in the study. (Babbie and Benaquisto, 2002).

Description of the Respondents

The respondents for this study were randomly selected grade 9 students enrolled in Gumaca National High School Gumaca, Quezon for the school year 2023-2024. Each student was provided with equal opportunity to indicate gender belongingness, ethnicity, place of residence, parental educational background, and nature of work. Furthermore, the respondents were asked whether they had done agriculture-related work and if they had relatives who had done agriculture-related work. Their perception towards Agri-Fishery specialization was gathered using both qualitative and quantitative methods.

Data Collection Procedures

A. Classroom Observation

Classroom observations were one of the techniques used in this study. It is part of the qualitative method indicated in this research study. This method was conducted at the beginning of the research process to gather insights into the students' attitudes and perceptions towards Agri-Fishery as a specialization subject in TLE. Moreover, to record all the activities that occurred during classroom observations, the researcher utilized reflective journaling. Classroom observation is conducted for a period of one

week and a half. During this period, the researcher gathered genuine reactions from the students because students were not informed that they were being observed.

Figure 1. Series of Classroom Observation.

A. Focus-Group Discussion (FGD)

Another method is through the conduct of focus-group discussions. Students were asked several questions to gather their perception of Agri-Fishery Specialization. The questionnaire contains open and close-ended questions. The use of open-ended questions is justified with the objective of bringing out rich and meaningful answers. Open-ended questions allow greater spontaneity and adaptation of the interaction between the researcher and the interviewed. FGD is done in order to obtain information about the current attitudes of students toward Agri-Fishery as a specialization subject when taught in a classroom, this method was utilized after the conduct of classroom observations. During the approximately 2-month observation period, the responses of the students were noted and categorized into general statements. To ensure the accurateness of the activity, the responses of the students were recorded. Also, the researcher ensured privacy and anonymity, the researcher

ensured that the secondary school students understood that no individual would be connected to any of the recorded activities.

Figure 2. Focus Group Discussion.

Self-made Questionnaire (5-point Likert Scale)

Data were collected using an instrument created by the researcher with the assistance of her graduate thesis adviser and two (2) master teachers at Gumaca National High School. The researcher personally administered the survey to the respondents to determine the attitude and perception of Gumaca National High School Students towards agriculture as a choice for TLE Specialization. Using the participant observation form and the self-made questionnaire, the quantitative collection methods proceeded. A 4-point Likert scale is used. The researcher made certain that the

Figure 3. Administration of Self-Made Questionnaire

benefits and limitations of each chosen data collection method were carefully considered throughout the research process.

To quantify the attitude perception of students towards Agri-Fishery, the quantitative method is utilized through the use of structured questionnaires. This is an appropriate technique used in acquiring large substantial information from a heterogenous sample, more specifically when there is a limiting factor such as time and resources. Since this method is conducted using the face-to-face strategy with the identified respondents, the researcher generated a very high response rate. This technique creates an opportunity to clarify confusion and misunderstanding on the different questions included in the questionnaire.

In addition, a self-made questionnaire was used to elicit information on students' demographic information and background which include age, religion, gender, ethnicity, as well as their experience in doing agriculture-related work, parental occupational choice and nature of work, and educational level of parents. Questions included in the first section contained information that led to the collection of students' information, agricultural background, parental occupational choice, and nature of work. Included in the second section were perception questions that were designed to gather information on the student's attitudes and perceptions toward agriculture. The students' attitudes and perceptions were gauged using a 4-point Likert-type scale; 4 for strongly agree, 3 for agree, 2 for disagree, and 1 for strongly disagree. For the students as respondents of this research study, this method may seem difficult in terms of relating to the 4-point Likert-type scale. However, when conducted and administered on a face-to-face basis, this method demonstrates complete understanding.

Data Analysis

To provide a richer and more nuanced understanding of the topic, this study employed a mixed-method approach in the collection of data, specifically the Exploratory Sequential Design. This method started with qualitative data collection to explore a phenomenon, and then used quantitative methods to test or generalize the initial findings. This approach offered an opportunity to draw from the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative research approaches.

A concurrent design is utilized, which combines quantitative and qualitative methods. This is done for the purpose of triangulation and complementarities. In 2011, Nweing defined a concurrent design in mixed method analysis using quantitative and qualitative approaches in parallel either for triangulation or complementation to answer various aspects of the overall research question. A combination of quantitative and qualitative results was done in order to provide a comprehensive and much more reliable analysis (Carvalho and White, 1997). In 2012, Bamberger highlighted the importance of using a mixed methods approach in enhancing the validity and credibility of evaluation findings. Moreover, Munday et al, 2011 pointed out that the use of a mixed-method approach strengthens the representativeness of in-depth qualitative studies by linking a case study to quantitative sampling.

Quantitative data was collected using a self-made questionnaire on randomly selected 205 grade 9 students enrolled at Gumaca National High School Gumaca, Quezon for the school year 2023-2024. This research study used Jamovi 2.3.16 as a statistical tool in carrying out the descriptive such as means and percentages to summarize quantitative data. Also, the Independent Sample T-Test, specifically the Mann-Whitney U test is carried out to measure the association between the respondents' perceptions towards Agri-Fishery Specialization and socioeconomic

status, cultural background, and familial influence. To be able to easily understand and interpret visual comparison of different variables measured in this study, the descriptive statistics were arranged and presented using frequency tables. Correlation tests between variables were carried out during hypothesis testing. This is utilized to decide on whether or not a relationship exists between variables discussed in this study. A descriptive and relational analysis was used to provide high inferential results of the correlation tests that were carried out as part of the attainment of the research objectives.

On the other hand, qualitative information used in this study is based on 10 focus group discussions. Information was collected through informal discussions with the students. Qualitative analysis of the information gathered through FGD is carried out. Direct quotations of key expressions (translated in English) were also used but the names of the students were not disclosed due to ethical reasons. With the use of the “interpretive approach”, specifically the coding and categorization, the qualitative section comprehensively summarized the quantitative analysis. This analysis started with transcribing the data generated from the focused group discussion conducted with the respondents. The descriptive interpretations of the observation notes were also made to give the researcher a better understanding of the students’ perception of Agri-Fishery. Moreover, to determine the factors that have a greater influence on the student’s attitude and perception towards Agri-Fishery, a descriptive analysis is performed.

Descriptive interpretation is done using an open coding method during classroom observation and interview notes. Open coding, also known as the analytical method, is explained as the identification and labeling of concepts (Strauss and Corbin, 1998). Cited by Babbie and Benaquisto in 2002, in an open-coding method, a concept

functions as the indicator of the abstract events, objects, or actions that a researcher identifies as being significant. This technique was useful in this study because it made it easier for the researcher to separate the qualitative data into discrete components and then categorize those parts into categories, meanings, or patterns that were comparable to one another.

IX. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results of the Classroom Observation, Focus Group Discussion, and Interview

A total of 4 classroom observations that determine the students' active participation in Agri-Fishery classes were conducted. Observation is done based on the class sectioning of the students. The researcher observed apparent disinterest during classroom discussions with students from sections 2 and 3 which was due to a variety of circumstances that appeared to impair their capacity to respond to questions. On the day of the scheduled observation, there were obvious signs of heat fatigue in this particular class which may be the reason for their low response rate. Moreover, during classroom teaching, most of the students keep on standing and look uncomfortable, highly distracted, and display a low level of interest and attentiveness in class. On the other hand, the locations of the other three (3) classes were observed to have proper ventilation, which is why the students show a feeling of comfort. Also, students in these classes show a higher level of response to questions compared to that of sections 2 and 3. In the study conducted by Ryzin in 2011, it is suggested that students should be provided with a school environment conducive to learning to effectively promote engagement, hope, and academic achievement. If this is done continuously, a significant increase in the academic performance of the students will be observed over time.

Table 1

Classroom Observation Results

Section	Response to Question	Attentiveness in Class
1	High	Average
2	Low	Low
3	Average	Low
4	High	High

5	High	High
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Source: Qualitative Analysis

**low – some students participate in classroom discussion*

Average – almost half of the class participate in classroom discussion

High – more than half of the class actively participate in classroom discussion

Key Influences on the Students' Choice of Area of Specialization

Key influences on the students' choice of area of specialization is identified through the conduct of focused group discussion. Students were interviewed using a structured questionnaire including open-ended questions. The answers of the students were noted, utilized, and presented in Table 4. The students' preference for a particular area of specialization is influenced by a variety of internal and external factors that are often within school control. Students' perceptions on whether what specialization to choose are influenced by familial and societal preferences, specifically their parents, teachers, peers, and the way how they see others give importance to a particular specialization. The Philippine agricultural sector is continuously experiencing an insignificant level of attention and importance from the government. As grade 9 learners, they might not learned this directly, but how their parents encouraged them to get themselves involved in a science-oriented or computer-related course makes them develop apathy for agriculture-related courses. This consequently affects the preference, as well as the urge of the students to get themselves associated with agriculture-related courses. This creates unfavorable impressions in the minds of students towards agriculture. More often than not, these influence motivational level, interest drive, and passion towards agriculture which in the long run may cause them to increase apathy in this field of study. With this understanding, the researcher included in the questionnaire several questions pertaining to these significant indicators to effectively identify the greatest factors that influence students'

occupational aspirations and how these factors influence their attitude and perception towards Agri-Fishery as their TLE Specialization.

The results show that 35 students mentioned that the basis in choosing their TLE specialization is based on their personal views and opinions while 38 students mentioned that their choice is influenced by their peers. On the other hand, 43 students stated that choosing TLE specialization is based on idealized views or prestige. Teacher factor is considered a factor in choosing their TLE specialization mentioned by 49 students. Second to the largest key influence is on parental factor with 64 times mentioned by the respondents. This indicates that students perceive that familial influence is one of the biggest factors influencing their perceptions towards choosing a specialization. The majority of the respondents reported that they chose Agri-Fishery mainly because their kin told them. This implies that there are still existing norms pertaining to the significant influence that relatives have on the students. The highest key influence falls on the availability of the TLE specialization as their basis for enrolling in a TLE specialization.

Table 2

Key Influences on the Students' Choice of TLE Specialization

Factors	Narrative Examples
Personal Interest	"Choosing TLE specialization is based on my own personal views and opinions" (mentioned by 35 students)
Peer Influence	<i>"I am influenced by my friends in choosing TLE Specialization"</i> (mentioned by 38 students)
Idealized views or prestige	<i>"I am affected by how others view the course or subject"</i> (mentioned by 43 students)
Teacher Factor	"My choice is affected by my fondness of the teacher handling the subject (mentioned by 49 students)
Parental Factor	<i>"My parents decide what to take as my TLE specialization"</i> (mentioned by 64 students)
Availability of TLE Specialization	<i>"Enrolled late and no more slot in my first-choice specialization"</i> (mentioned by 130 students)

Source: Qualitative Analysis

Reasons Given for Studying Agri-Fishery

The experiences of students during their formal education in secondary schools significantly influence their choice of what course to pursue. With this understanding, the researcher asked the respondents to indicate and give reasons for choosing Agri-Fishery Specialization in school.

A total of 126 respondents (62.37%) reasoned out that choosing Agri-Fishery as their TLE specialization due to the availability of slots, while 29 (14.36%) of students stated that they are very fond of a teacher who handles Agri-Fishery specialization. A total of 15 (7.43%) of students perceive Agri-Fishery as an interesting subject. A total of 14 (6.93%) students chose Agri-Fishery because their parents asked them to do so. The same percentage (6.93%) of students indicated that Agri-Fishery is an important subject that a student should study.

This is similar to the findings in Rayfiled et al., study on “Factors that Influence Student Decisions to Enroll in a College of Agriculture and Life Sciences”. Based on their study, it was concluded that 18.1% contributed to parental factors when choosing a major among college students.

Table 3

Reasons for Choosing Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization

Reasons	Frequency	Percent
I want to pursue Agriculture in college	4	1.98
My parents asked me to take Agri-Fishery as my TLE Specialization	14	6.93
It is an important subject that a student should study	14	6.93
It is an interesting subject	15	7.43
Students' fondness with Agriculture teacher	29	14.36
More available slots in Agri-Fishery	126	62.37
Total	202	100

Key statements gathered from focus group discussions and interviews were summarized into 10 perception questions. To answer the first objective of this study stated as “identify the level of attitude among grade 9 students towards Agri-Fishery specialization”, students were involved in a focus group discussion and were asked to answer several question that pertains to their experiences and perceptions towards Agri-Fishery in Gumaca National High School. Each item in the Likert-scale questionnaire was rated based on a four-point scale (Strongly Agree-4, Agree-3, Disagree-2, and Strongly Disagree-1). This was used to calculate a mean rating score for all students. Therefore, the maximum mean rating score of an individual respondent could have been four and a minimum of one. This mean rating score reflected the respondents’ perception. For a mean rating score between 0- 2.5, perception was coded as negative perception. On the other hand, mean rating scores of 2.5 and above were coded positive perception. Each item had a possible mean rating score of four and a minimum of one. The students’ perception scores are presented in Table 1. This summarizes the students’ level of perception towards Agri-Fishery at Gumaca National High School Gumaca, Quezon.

Table 4

Mean Scores of Students Towards Agri-Fishery Specialization

Statement	N	Mean	MR
1. Agri-Fishery specialization provides me with valuable hands-on experience with practical applications and relevant to the real world scenario	205	2.91	1 st
2. The topics, learning tasks, and activities included in the current curriculum guide are aligned with my expectations, interests and career aspirations.	204	2.30	7 th
3. I believe that Agri-Fishery is given enough emphasis or importance in school and by the organization as a whole	205	1.95	9 th

4. I believe that the skills and knowledge I acquire through Agri-Fishery will be beneficial in my future endeavors.	205	1.83	4 th
5. Growing up with relatives who work in the agricultural sector has inspired me to consider Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization	205	3.14	2 nd
6. My family's history of involvement in agriculture positively influences my interest in pursuing Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization	205	2.85	3 rd
7. There is a high level of visibility and recognition of Agri-Fishery in society and its given value and importance.	205	1.81	5 th
8. Taking Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization also means receiving mockery from peers	205	2.85	10 th
9. Choosing Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization provides me with a high level of integrity	205	1.91	6 th
10. I feel encouraged from pursuing Agri-Fishery because I believe there are lots of career opportunities in this field.	204	2.19	8 th

Note. Scale Values: 1 = Strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Agree; 4 = Strongly Agree (<2.5 = negative; ≥2.5=positive) *p<0.05

For the students' perception as shown in table 1, an average mean rating score of 2.38 is computed. This implies a negative perception towards Agri-Fishery in general. Table 5 presented 3 statements out of 10 that were rated above 2.5. This means that on these statements, students have positive perception of Agri-Fishery as their TLE specialization.

Table 5

Positive Perception of Students Towards Agri-Fishery

Statement	N	Mean
<i>1. Agriculture specialization provides me with valuable hands-on experience with practical applications and relevant to the real world scenario</i>	205	2.91
<i>5. Growing up with relatives who work in the agricultural sector has inspired me to consider Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization</i>	205	3.14
<i>1. My family's history of involvement in agriculture positively influences my interest in pursuing Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization</i>	205	2.85

The table above shows that students have a positive perception of the Agri-Fishery specialization because they were able to experience hands-on activities. Some of the positive perceptions were reflected in the students' relatives' involvement in agriculture-related works. The students who have a positive perception towards specialization are due to familial influence. This is in line with the result of the study conducted by Ehigbor and Akinlosotu in 2016 where they found a significant relationship between parents' involvement in agriculture and their children's choice of specialization in public secondary schools. However, it was also recommended that parents should cautiously avoid pushing their children into pursuing something beyond their will just to accomplish their own failings.

Mean ratings found to have negative perceptions towards Agri-Fishery specialization were reflected on 7 out of 10 items (table 6).

Table 6

Negative Perception of Students Towards Agri-Fishery

Statement	N	Mean
2. The topics, learning tasks, and activities included in the current curriculum guide are aligned with my expectations, interests and career aspirations.	204	2.30
3. I believe that agriculture education is given enough emphasis or importance in school and by the organization as a whole	205	1.95
4. I believe that the skills and knowledge I acquire through agriculture education will be beneficial in my future endeavors.	205	1.83
7. There is a high level of visibility and recognition of agriculture education in society and its given value and importance.	205	1.81
8. Taking Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization increases popularity in school	205	2.89
9. Choosing Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization provides me with a high level of integrity	205	1.91
10. I feel encouraged from pursuing agriculture education because I believe there are lots of career opportunities in this field.	204	2.19

On the other hand, the two lowest mean ratings computed were 1.81 and 1.83 “There is a high level of visibility and recognition of agriculture education in society and its given value and importance” and “I believe that the skills and knowledge I acquire through agriculture education will be beneficial in my future endeavors”. This is the sad reality that agriculture is facing in terms of the recognition given to it by others. This implies that students fear being judged by their classmates once they are involved in agriculture education. This also means that students do not regard taking the course as a career that will provide better opportunities for themselves as well as for their families. This is an expression that choosing Agri-Fishery provides students with a low level of recognition and integrity. More often than not, students are not encouraged to continue their association with being called “agriculture majors”. The content of the curriculum guide used in teaching Agri-Fishery prepares students to be work-ready. However, these students are longing to experience a more scientific approach in studying Agriculture rather than actual farm work. The need to revisit the content standard of the K12 curriculum is deemed necessary for the alignment of students’ interests, expectations, and career aspirations.

Similar to the findings of Ball et al. in 2003, the teacher participants in this study displayed a negative perception of the effectiveness of the curriculum guide used in teaching Agri-Fishery Specialization as a major contributing factor to the overall academic and personal development of students. Although students see the effectiveness and alignment of learning tasks and activities, this is only because of the engaging learning tasks and activities employed by the teacher in the classroom. Nonetheless, the majority of the learning tasks were found to be misaligned with the students’ expectations, aspirations, and dreams.

Internal and External Factors Influencing Students' Choice of Specialization

A. Gender of the Respondents

A total of 94 or 45.85% represented the male population while 111 or 54.15% represented the female population. Using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov or the K-S test statistics, there is a significant difference between students' attitudes and perceptions towards agriculture and gender. With an asymptotic significance of .364 (p-value <.001), the null hypothesis was rejected at the 5% significance level. The result further implies that male and female students have different perspectives in choosing Agri-Fishery as their TLE specialization. The result of the K-S test signifies that students' preference in choosing Agri-Fishery as their TLE specialization is influenced by the student's gender..

Table 7

Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	94	45.85
Female	111	54.14
Total	205	100

B. Residence of the Respondents

Regarding the respondents' place of residence, a total of 200 out of 205 participants responded to this question. A total of 161 or 78.54% of the population resided within the town, while only 39, or 19.01% lived in barrios. Five participants did not respond to this question. Descriptive statistics of the respondents by place of residence are presented in Table 8.

The living environment of students is another important factor that influences their perception of a course of study. The way how the students construct ideas, and

display attitudes or perceptions toward agriculture is dependent on their environment. Frequent interaction with someone who is working in the field provides students with a positive outlook and impression of agriculture. This led to the significant realization and appreciation of the importance of various agricultural activities. Upon learning this, the researcher indicated the students' living environment in one of the questions in the self-made questionnaire. Table 8 shows that 161 or 78.54% of the respondents lived in the urban areas while 39 or 19.01% of the respondents lived in the rural areas.

Using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) normality test statistic, it is found that there is a significant difference in the student's attitudes and perceptions towards agriculture and their living environment. Having computed an asymptotic significance of 0.372 (p-value <.001), using the 0.05 significant level, the null hypothesis was rejected. The result further implies that students who were exposed to rural environments have positive attitudes and perceptions towards agriculture. Students' preference in choosing Agri-Fishery as their TLE specialization is motivated by their living environment. Likewise, students living within the town have a low level of interest in choosing Agri-Fishery as a course of study.

Table 8

Residence of the Students

Residence	Frequency	Percent
town (within the urban barangays)	161	78.54
barrio (far flung areas)	39	19.01
No response	5	2.44
Total	205	100

C. Participants' Ethnicity

A total of 185 or 90.24% of the students indicated that they belong to Tagalog ethnicity while only 18 or 8.78% indicated non-tagalog as their ethnicity. There are 2 respondents who did not respond to this question.

Using the Kruskal-Wallis test statistics, attitudes and perceptions of students towards agriculture significantly differ on their ethnicity. The null hypothesis was tested using the rejected resulting in a significant difference between the two variables being tested. The frequencies for both the "students' consideration to choose Agri-Fishery as their TLE Specialization" and "perception that Agri-Fishery is as important as other non-agriculture TLE " parents' educational were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis test statistic.

With a significance level of 5%, the asymptotic significance of 1.011 (p-value 0.315) for students' perception that Agri-Fishery is as important as other non-agriculture TLE specialization" 0.556 (p-value 0.456) for "I will consider Agri-Fishery as my TLE Specialization" showed that there is a significant difference. Accepting the null hypothesis further means that most students do not consider Agri-Fishery for TLE specialization. This further means that the choice of students of TLE specialization does not depend on the students' ethnic group

Table 9

Students' Ethnic Background

	Students	Percentage
Tagalog	185	90.24
Non-tagalog	18	8.78
No response	2	0.98
Total	376	100

D. Students' Perspectives Towards Agri-Fishery

Among all TLE Specialization in Gumaca National High School, Agri-Fishery ranks the top 2-3 lowest. (Enrolment Data 2019-2023). For the past several years, agriculture has been the least popular chosen specialization path amongst the students at Gumaca National High School. During the conduct of the classroom survey, students were asked whether Agri-Fishery was as important as other TLE Specializations. Students' responses to this question are presented and summarized in table 10.

Table 10

Agriculture as Important as Other TLE Specialization

Response	Frequency	Percent
Yes	58	28.29
No	143	60.76
undecided	4	1.95
Total	205	100

Out of 205 student respondents, 143, or 60.76% believe agriculture isn't as important as other TLE specializations in Gumaca National High School while 58, or 28.29% believe that Agri-Fishery is an important TLE Specialization. There are four students who did not respond to the questions. As for their reasons, the majority of the students stated that agriculture is a menial work which their classmates viewed as a course with fewer future opportunities.

The null hypothesis was rejected using the Kruskal-Wallis test statistic resulting in an asymptotic significance of 0.01, using a 0.05 significant level. This means that students who prefer Agri-Fishery consider this specialization in their TLE subject.

E. Occupation of Parents of the Students

Table 11 shows the different occupations of the students. Occupation is grouped and divided into six categories. Approximately, 5.82% and 16.58% of the father and mothers respectively were unskilled workers. On the other hand, 24.34% and 29.02% of the fathers and mothers respectively fall under the professionals category. The lowest percentage of mothers is considered “skilled” accounting for 8.29%. Further, 22.75% are businessmen or managers of their own businesses while 18.65% of the mothers are involved in menial jobs (mostly online selling). A percentage of 17.10% of the mothers and 13.76% of the fathers are working as teaching and non-teaching personnel..

Based on the result of the Kruskal-Wallis test statistic, a significant difference between parents’ occupational level and the student’s attitude and perception towards the choice of Agri-Fishery is tested. Using a significance level of 5%, the computed asymptotic significance of less than 0.05 (computed = <.001) for the father occupation and (computed = 0.001) for the mother occupation showed that there is a significant difference between the variables being tested.

Table 11

Occupation of Parents of the Students

	FREQUENCY		PERCENT	
	Father	Mother	Father	Mother
Unskilled/Unemp	11	32	5.82	16.58
Skilled	23	16	12.17	8.29
Education	26	33	13.76	17.10
Government	40	20	21.16	10.36
Business/Managers	43	36	22.75	18.65
Professionals	46	56	24.34	29.02
Total	189	193	100	100

F. Parents' Educational Level

Based on the table below, 39.15% of the fathers and 29.74% of the mothers of the respondents had university degrees, indicating that most of the fathers had more education than their mothers.

The frequencies for both the mother and father's level of education and the student's attitude and perception towards Agri-Fishery were computed using the Kruskal-Wallis test statistic. Using a 5% level of significance, the asymptotic significance of 0.0520 (p-value computed = 0.002) for the father's education and 0.0288 (p-value computed = 0.019) for the mother's education showed that the difference is statistically significant. There is a significant difference between parents' educational level and the student's attitude and perception towards Agri-Fishery. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This finding is similar to the result of the study conducted in 2012 by Waseem and Zari. Their study considered the influence of their parent's education as one of the major factors that affects the choice of course of study among students.

Table 12

Educational Level Attained by the Parents

	FREQUENCY		PERCENT	
	Father	Mother	Father	Mother
No formal educ	9	20	4.76	10.26
Elementary Graduate	14	21	7.41	10.77
High School Graduate	70	63	37.04	32.31
Vocational Grad	22	33	11.64	16.92
College Grad	74	58	39.15	29.74
Total	189	195	100	100

G. Students' Exposure to Agriculture-Related Activities

Experience in doing agriculture-related work provides career awareness among students. This also includes the opportunity to experience practical and actual training. Making the students realize that agricultural work is more than the majority's perception of a type of work that requires physical labor and manual employment, enables students to instill favorable attitudes and perceptions toward agriculture. Based on this premise, the respondents were asked about their prior experiences in agriculture throughout the questionnaire session. Table 8 shows that a total of 60 or 29.27% of the students have experienced doing agriculture-related work while 145 or 63.30% do not have.

The null hypothesis was also tested using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test statistic. And with the computed asymptotic significance of 0.369 (p-value computed = $<.001$), using the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. This further means that there is a significant difference between students' attitudes and perceptions towards agriculture and the opportunity to perform agriculture-related work experience. The result further implies that students who have experience in agriculture-related work are more likely to choose Agri-Fishery as their TLE specialization.

Table 13

Students' Agriculture-Related Experience

	Students	
	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	60	29.27
No	145	70.73
Total	205	100

H. Relatives' Experience in Agriculture-Related Careers

Around 58.51% (220) indicated that they have experienced doing agriculture-related work while only 36.17% (136) indicated that they do not have relatives with agriculture-related work experience. Most of the students have relatives with agriculture-related experience (table 3). Twenty (20) student participants did not respond to this question.

The previously stated null hypothesis was tested using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test statistic. With the computed asymptotic significance of 0.418 (p-value computed = <.001), the null hypothesis was rejected using the 5% level of significance. This further implies that there is a significant difference between the students' attitude and perception towards agriculture and having relatives with experience in doing agriculture-related work. The result further implies that students who have relatives with agriculture-related experience are more likely to choose Agri-Fishery as their TLE specialization.

Table 14

Relatives' Experience in Agricultural related Careers

	students	
	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	87	42.44
No	114	55.61
No response	4	1.95
Total	205	100

Results of Correlation Tests

The third objective of this study was to compare the perceptions of students towards agriculture by gender, ethnicity, residence, experience doing agriculture work, and having relatives with experience in agriculture work. Students' perceptions that

were collected using the Likert Scale questionnaire were correlated with gender, ethnicity, residence, experience in agriculture work, and having relatives with experience in agriculture work only.

Perception of Students Towards Agri-Fishery and Students' Gender

Table 15 shows the mean rating scores of male and female respondents in each perception statement. There were 3 out of 10 items were found to have a significant difference between students' gender and their perceptions towards Agri-Fishery specialization with a p-value of 0.006. The computed mean for male and female respondents were 2.47 and 2.16 respectively. Males perceived the topics, learning tasks, and activities in Agri-Fishery as a factor in choosing Agri-Fishery as their area of specialization. Another test of significance that yields a positive correlation is in terms of the influence of growing up with relatives who have agricultural backgrounds. A p-value of 0.002 is computed with mean scores of 2.98 and 3.32 for female and male respondents. Again, it is among male respondents where a higher mean rating is computed. This means that male students agreed that living with relatives with agricultural backgrounds influences their choice of specialization. For perception statement number 10 "I feel encouraged from pursuing agriculture education because I believe there are lots of career opportunities in this field", the value of mean ratings of 2.08 and 2.31 were computed for female and male respondents respectively. Although this has resulted in a negative perception towards agriculture, talking about the gender of the respondents, males perceived Agri-Fishery more positively than females.

Table 15*Mean Scores Students' Perceptions and Gender*

Perception Statements of agriculture students towards agriculture education	Mean Rating			p value
	Grand (n=205)	M (94)	F (110)	
Agriculture specialization provides me with valuable hands-on experience with practical applications and relevant to the real world scenario	204	2.96	2.87	0.507
The topics, learning tasks, and activities included in the current curriculum guide are aligned with my expectations, interests and career aspirations.	205	2.43	2.18	0.031*
I believe that agriculture education is given enough emphasis or importance in school and by the organization as a whole	205	1.94	1.96	0.786
I believe that the skills and knowledge I acquire through agriculture education will be beneficial in my future endeavors.	205	1.87	1.80	0.461
Growing up with relatives who work in the agricultural sector has inspired me to consider Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization	205	3.26	3.04	0.048*
My family's history of involvement in agriculture positively influences my interest in pursuing Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization	205	2.85	2.88	0.013*
There is a high level of visibility and recognition of agriculture education in society and its given value and importance.	205	1.77	1.86	0.295
Taking Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization also means receiving mockery from peers	205	1.95	1.84	0.283
Choosing Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization provides me with a high level of integrity	205	1.90	1.93	0.808
I feel encouraged from pursuing agriculture education because I believe there are lots of career opportunities in this field.	205	2.31	2.08	0.035*

Note: $H_a \mu_F \neq \mu_M$

^a Levene's test is significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting a violation of the assumption of equal variances.

Note. Scale Values: 1 = Strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Agree; 4 = Strongly Agree (<2.5 = negative; ≥ 2.5 =positive) * $p < 0.05$

Students' Perceptions and Ethnicity

Table 16 shows the mean ratings of the different perception statements given to the respondents. The mean ratings between the different ethnicities resulted in insignificant differences. Looking at the p values for each statement, there is no significant difference computed. This means that regardless of students' ethnicity, their choice of TLE specialization is not directly influenced.

Table 16

Mean Scores of Students' Perception Towards Agri-Fishery and Their Ethnicity

Perception Statements of agriculture students towards agriculture education	Mean Rating			p value
	Grand (n=203)	T (185)	NT (18)	
Agriculture specialization provides me with valuable hands-on experience with practical applications and relevant to the real world scenario	202	2.90	2.94	0.851
The topics, learning tasks, and activities included in the current curriculum guide are aligned with my expectations, interests and career aspirations.	201	2.29	2.22	0.722
I believe that agriculture education is given enough emphasis or importance in school and by the organization as a whole	203	1.97	1.72	0.164
I believe that the skills and knowledge I acquire through agriculture education will be beneficial in my future endeavors.	202	1.84	1.72	0.488
Growing up with relatives who work in the agricultural sector has inspired me to consider Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization	203	3.15	3.00	0.458
My family's history of involvement in agriculture positively influences my interest in pursuing Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization	203	2.87	2.83	0.860
There is a high level of visibility and recognition of agriculture education in society and its given value and importance.	202	1.80	1.94	0.384
Taking Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization also means receiving mockery from peers	203	1.89	1.89	0.989
Choosing Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization provides me with a high level of integrity	201	1.90	2.00	0.542

I feel encouraged from pursuing agriculture education because I believe there are lots of career opportunities in this field.	201	2.19	2.06	0.471
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Note: $H_a \mu_F \neq \mu_M$

^a Levene's test is significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting a violation of the assumption of equal variances.

Note. Scale Values: 1 = Strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Agree; 4 = Strongly Agree (<2.5 = negative; ≥ 2.5 =positive) * $p < 0.05$

Students' Perceptions and Living Environment

Table 17 shows the mean rating scores of students from different living environments. Higher mean ratings of 3.14 and 3.15 were reported under the statement "Growing up with relatives who work in the agricultural sector has inspired me to consider Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization" while the lowest mean rating of 1.86 and 2.05 was reported under the statement "Taking Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization also means receiving mockery from peers".

Looking at the p-values for the independent sample t-test conducted to test the significant difference between the place of students' residence, most of the perception statements indicate that the living environment is an important factor in the decision-making made by the respondents. Most of the respondents living in the barrio have a positive perception of agriculture. Higher values of mean ratings were observed from students' responses living in the barrio (rural areas). On the other hand, students living within the town reported relatively lower mean rating scores. The results justify that the place of residence or the living environment of the students greatly affects their choice of what course or area of specialization.

Table 17

Mean Scores of Students' Perception Towards Agri-Fishery and Their Living Environment

Perception Statements of agriculture students towards agriculture education	Mean Rating			p value
	Grand (n=200)	Barrio (39)	Town (161)	
Agriculture specialization provides me with valuable hands-on experience with practical applications and relevant to the real world scenario	199	2.95	2.91	<.001*
The topics, learning tasks, and activities included in the current curriculum guide are aligned with my expectations, interests and career aspirations.	199	2.38	2.27	0.002*
I believe that agriculture education is given enough emphasis or importance in school and by the organization as a whole	200	2.10	1.93	0.188
I believe that the skills and knowledge I acquire through agriculture education will be beneficial in my future endeavors.	199	2.11	1.79	0.011*
Growing up with relatives who work in the agricultural sector has inspired me to consider Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization	200	3.15	3.14	<.001*
My family's history of involvement in agriculture positively influences my interest in pursuing Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization	200	2.92	2.84	0.014*
There is a high level of visibility and recognition of agriculture education in society and its given value and importance.	200	2.11	1.77	<.001*
Taking Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization also means receiving mockery from peers	200	2.05	1.86	<.001*
Choosing Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization provides me with a high level of integrity	200	2.03	1.91	<.001*
I feel encouraged from pursuing agriculture education because I believe there are lots of career opportunities in this field.	198	2.15	2.18	0.835

Note: $H_a \mu_F \neq \mu_M$

^a Levene's test is significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting a violation of the assumption of equal variances.

Note. Scale Values: 1 = Strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Agree; 4 = Strongly Agree (<2.5 = negative; ≥ 2.5 =positive) * $p < 0.05$

Students' Perceptions and Having Relatives with Experience Doing Agriculture-Related Work

Table 18 shows that a total of 8 out of 10 statements with p-values less than 0.05 were found to have a significant association between student perception and having relatives with experience doing agriculture-related work.

In most of the statements pertaining to the perception of students towards agriculture, significant differences were seen as compared to having relatives with experience in agriculture-related work. The findings are similar to the study conducted by Stair, Blackburn, and Bunch in 2016 where one of the factors that influence agriculture students' choice of academic major is having a family member or relative in the agriculture sector. Furthermore, they emphasize that the association between students' perception of agriculture and having someone who has experience in the field drives a student to express respect and admiration.

The result further implies that students having relatives with agriculture-related experience and students without relatives having agriculture-related experience have different perceptions pertaining to pursuing agriculture as a course of study. The former considered pursuing agriculture in the coming years while the latter did not. However, based on the statistics pertaining to the number of students with relatives and without relatives doing agriculture work, more students responded that they do not have relatives with agriculture-related experience. Thus, there is still a greater number of students who did not consider agriculture specialization on top of their choices. The reason for this significant difference is mainly because of familial history and influence on their interest in pursuing the course.

Table 18

Mean Scores of Students' Perception Towards Agri-Fishery and Having Relatives with Experience Doing Agriculture-Related Work

Perception Statements of agriculture students towards agriculture education	Mean Rating			p value
	Grand (n=205)	with (114)	w/o (91)	
Agriculture specialization provides me with valuable hands-on experience with practical applications and relevant to the real world scenario	200	2.95	2.87	0.506
The topics, learning tasks, and activities included in the current curriculum guide are aligned with my expectations, interests and career aspirations.	199	2.37	2.24	0.247
I believe that agriculture education is given enough emphasis or importance in school and by the organization as a whole	201	1.97	1.95	0.861
I believe that the skills and knowledge I acquire through agriculture education will be beneficial in my future endeavors.	200	1.83	1.84	0.868
Growing up with relatives who work in the agricultural sector has inspired me to consider Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization	201	3.11	3.14	0.823
My family's history of involvement in agriculture positively influences my interest in pursuing Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization	201	2.90	2.81	0.454
There is a high level of visibility and recognition of agriculture education in society and its given value and importance.	200	1.81	1.82	0.912
Taking Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization also means receiving mockery from peers	201	1.92	1.87	0.619
Choosing Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization provides me with a high level of integrity	201	1.91	1.93	0.825
I feel encouraged from pursuing agriculture education because I believe there are lots of career opportunities in this field.	199	2.23	2.14	0.402

Note: $H_a \mu_F \neq \mu_M$

^a Levene's test is significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting a violation of the assumption of equal variances.

Note. Scale Values: 1 = Strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Agree; 4 = Strongly Agree (<2.5 = negative; ≥ 2.5 =positive) * $p < 0.05$

Students' Perception Towards Agriculture and Experience Doing Agriculture-Related Work

Table 19 shows that 7 out of 10 statements were found to have a significant difference between students' perception towards agriculture and experience doing agriculture-related work. Students who have done agricultural-related work expressed a positive perception of agriculture. These students see the learning experiences as more valuable and express appreciation for the alignment of tasks and activities and their expectations, interests, and career aspirations.

Further, more than one-third of the students have no experience doing agriculture-related work, inside and outside school. Most of the students chose non-agriculture participation as their TLE Specialization. Also, there are no organizations in school that are related to agriculture. As the population starts to rise, alongside the change in the norms and culture in the society, the younger generations become isolated from the agriculture era. This indicates that there is a need to revisit strategies to motivate and inspire these younger generations to increase their apathy in agriculture and consider Agri-Fishery as their TLE specialization. Rayfield et al., in 2013 reported that agriculture-related hobbies were also influential in the student's choice to get themselves involved in the course.

Table 19

Mean Scores of Students' Perception Towards Agri-Fishery and Experience in Doing Agriculture-Related Work

Perception Statements of agriculture students towards agriculture education	Mean Rating			p value
	Grand (n=205)	Yes (145)	No (60)	
Agri-Fishery specialization provides me with valuable hands-on experience with practical applications and relevant to the real world scenario	204	3.62	2.62	<.001*

The topics, learning tasks, and activities included in the current curriculum guide are aligned with my expectations, interests and career aspirations.	204	2.57	2.18	0.002*
I believe that Agri-Fishery is given enough emphasis or importance in school and by the organization as a whole	205	2.03	1.92	0.299
I believe that the skills and knowledge I acquire through Agri-Fishery will be beneficial in my future endeavors.	204	1.97	1.78	0.082
Growing up with relatives who work in the agricultural sector has inspired me to consider agriculture education as a career path.	205	3.82	2.86	<.001*
My family's history of involvement in agriculture positively influences my interest in pursuing agriculture education.	205	3.07	2.79	0.029*
There is a high level of visibility and recognition of agriculture education in society and its given value and importance.	205	2.08	1.71	<.001*
There is no judgment from peers for showing interest in agriculture education	205	2.25	1.74	<.001*
I feel encouraged from pursuing agriculture education because I believe there are lots of career opportunities in the field.	205	2.25	1.78	<.001*
I consider taking agriculture rather than other academic disciplines.	205	2.18	2.19	0.963

Note: $H_a \mu_F \neq \mu_M$

^a Levene's test is significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting a violation of the assumption of equal variances.

Note. Scale Values: 1 = Strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Agree; 4 = Strongly Agree (<2.5 = negative; ≥ 2.5 =positive) * $p < 0.05$

Implications of the Findings of the Study

This section contains the findings of the study and its implications for teaching Agri-Fishery at Gumaca National High School. Furthermore, the results stated in this section will provide the basis for the development, creation, and/or adoption of certain policies or laws that could shift students' negative perception to positive perception towards Agri-Fishery as a TLE specialization. Further, the results of this study may lead to curriculum enhancement for Agriculture specialization. Since there is a statement that some of the learning competencies included in the curriculum guide are

not aligned with the students' expectations, interests, and future career goals, the findings can lead the way for the modification of learning competencies included in the curriculum guide. On the other hand, teaching methods or strategies are found to be particularly effective for the students, especially in hands-on performance. With this, teachers should be informed that to always provide the students with hands-on learning experiences because that makes them engage effectively in learning. Based on the 2-month classroom observation, the students reacted positively to the collaborative and engaging activities used in teaching topics in Agri-Fishery. Students tend to enjoy more performance tasks compared to the theoretical discussion. They want to learn through the actual performance of the task. These can effectively address the gap identified in this study regarding students' perception of Agri-Fishery. Moreover, teachers handling Agri-Fishery can adopt this practice to promote and maintain a positive learning environment in the classroom. Through these, students might find a connection between the knowledge and skills learned and their benefits to their future endeavors.

The authenticity of the activity enables students to create connections to the real world, to their everyday lives, as well as to practice in the discipline (Newmann, Marks, & Gamoran, 1996).

In terms of very low expression and aspiration among students to pursue agriculture due to lack of knowledge in terms of opportunities in agriculture, findings of this study may lead to the strengthening of student support services which might include tutoring programs, academic counseling, or extracurricular activities related to agriculture. The school itself can develop programs that could encourage students to choose Agri-Fishery as their TLE specialization.

Students express higher agreement in terms of the influence that their family and kin provide when choosing the field of study. Parental influence on students' choices emerged as a key theme in their decision-making process. This elaborates on the meaning of support systems and experiences that can aid professional practice for supporting the career decision-making process. With this, it is also necessary that parents should be involved in academic counseling. School heads, teachers, and guidance counselors should develop counseling programs to inform parents regarding the important role they have in shaping their children's decision-making capabilities.

Another factor that seems to be evident as to why students don't want to choose Agri-Fishery is because of the poor recognition and importance given to agriculture in society. With this, there is a much more effort that the government needs to do to strengthen agricultural education in the country. Exposure to agriculture-related activities and programs in school and in the community may lead to increased recognition of the society for agriculture. The school's initiative to encourage students to participate in activities inside and outside school may provide students with greater opportunities to students to achieve something that they can be proud of. Students who were able to participate in a contest for instance develop a sense of relatedness. In Gumaca National High School, there are very few instances in which students participated in a school-based or community-based contest due to the reason the fact that students think less of the course. Through positive interactions received from peers and teachers such as respect, caring, and interest in students' well-being, a sense of belongingness is met. Students will be more likely to feel a sense of relatedness of belongingness. Satisfaction of relatedness needs enhances students' interest, participation, and academic effort (Wentzel, 1997).

Another dramatic result is in terms of how students perceive Agri-Fishery in terms of future opportunities. The majority of the students were not encouraged to pursue agriculture education because I believe there are lots of career opportunities in the field. The implication of this finding is that schools should invite personalities who graduated from an Agri-related course to be the guest speakers during graduation and moving up, or speakers in a symposium or training. The Local Government Unit (LGU) may craft policy pertaining to the involvement of the youths in barangay services in a Clean and Green Project for instance. The school may also coordinate with the LGU for the establishment of a barangay garden which will be spearheaded by the youths. Equivalent recognition may be given to students who will succeed in the said activity. Through these simple activities, students will realize how important they are being associated with activities that have a relationship with agriculture.

X. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

Based on the problem of the study, the research question and null hypotheses that directed it, as well as the results of the statistical analyses, it is concluded as follows:

1. Parental occupation and educational attainment significantly influence grade 9 high school students in choosing Agri-Fishery and another agriculture-related course as their area of specialization. This implies that schools should develop a strong parent-teacher relationship that will strengthen stakeholders' involvement and participation with their children in choosing areas of specialization. Parents should be encouraged to be with their children at the time that they are about to choose specialization. It is not about prohibiting their freedom to choose what they want to pursue, but it is just giving them some support that could clear cloud judgment for certain decisions.

2. The living environment is another important factor in grade 9 students' positive perception towards agriculture. With this, schools should plan field works, field trips, and farm exposure to students to encourage them to enroll and venture into Agri-Fishery Specialization.

3. Students with agriculture-related experience have a positive attitude and perception towards agriculture. This implies that schools should expose students to more agriculture-related activities during homeroom guidance hours. Further, elementary and secondary schools should initiate and support in organizing guilds and groups as part of extra-curricular activities of the students with advocacies on strengthening agricultural education. This will encourage students to choose Agri-

Fishery as their area of specialization in Technology and Livelihood Education subject. Parents and teachers should encourage students to participate in various organizations led by the Local Government Unit (LGU) for exposure to much more comprehensive agriculture-related activities and programs. These programs will make students see the importance of agriculture and hopefully, the students' misconceptions about agriculture will be eliminated because they will finally realize the importance of agriculture as an area to specialize.

4. Relatives of students with agriculture-related experience are also found to have a significant effect on the student's choice of Agri-Fishery as a TLE specialization. With this, teachers should conduct frequent home visitations to strengthen collaboration and relationships with parent-stakeholders. This will initiate a positive relationship with the parents and an effective way of constantly reminding parents to involve their children in agriculture-related activities, especially during after-school hours (weekends).

5. The Department of Education should continue to implement the *Gulayan sa Paaraan* Program (GPP) for the students to have direct participation in agriculture at the school level. This program will provide students with genuine experience which will encourage them to choose Agri-Fishery as their TLE specialization.

6. Although a significant percentage of students show positive perception towards Agri-Fishery, they do not have plans to study or pursue a career in agriculture after high school due to the perception that there are no opportunities in the field of Agriculture.

Recommendations

Based on the anticipated findings of this research, the following specific, actionable recommendations are provided for policymakers, schools, educators, and agriculture organizations:

1. Replication of the Research

This study should be replicated. The findings of the study can be used in the conduct of other research to determine if the findings differ significantly across cultures. Conducting studies that discuss cultural attitudes towards agriculture in the community or region may provide significant analysis that could strengthen the result of this study. Furthermore, a follow-up study that will include broader educational policies, curriculum design, or teaching methodologies could provide a more comprehensive analysis of the educational context and will also help strengthen the result generated from this undertaking.

2. Intensified Practical and Hands-On Learning Experiences

The school and the teachers should sustain or increase opportunities for hands-on learning by the utilization of school gardens under the *Gulayan sa Paaralan* Program (GPP) to provide students with more practical and hands-on learning of agricultural education. Through this, students will realize how important Agri-Fishery is as a course of specialization. Experiential learning enhances student engagement and retention (Bawden, 2015). Furthermore, the conduct of farm field trips should be initiated because these expose students to updates on agricultural education can also be initiated. The use of miniatures and models in teaching the course also poses a significant increase in students' motivation and academic performance (Sabuelba, 2023)

Figure 4. Gulayan sa Paaralan as venue of the students for hands-on activities.

The school and the teacher should consider collaboration with other secondary schools within the municipality to provide and gain materials and mentorship for

practical hands-on experience. Active participation during the conduct of career guidance which discusses opportunities in the agriculture industry may also pose positive output in providing students with knowledge of agriculture industry career opportunities.

Figure 5. Gardening collaboration with other schools and agencies.

The Department of Education should allow additional funding for activities that prioritize experiential learning such as the purchase of agricultural technologies that can be used and operated by the students. Policymakers, during the development and revision of the curriculum, should consider farm visitation to be a part of the performance task in the agriculture curriculum to develop partnerships with local farms. These activities provide the school and the students with strengthened partnerships with other stakeholders and agricultural organizations.

3. Innovation and Modernization of Agricultural Curriculum

Encourage more teachers to participate in the revision of the Agri-Fishery curriculum to provide reliable insights on the role of agriculture in addressing global changes such as food security and climate change. In a 2017 study conducted by Nugen, it was highlighted that the alignment of the new generation's interest with sustainability and innovation is very important in the increased interest of students in

agriculture-related subjects. Utilization of models and miniatures in teaching should be sustained by teachers handling Agri-Fishery specialization. This initiative increases students' engagement in the classroom teaching-learning process (Sabuelba, 2023).

Figure 6. Utilization of models and miniatures in teaching agriculture.

In addition, to ensure that the curriculum is appealing to the younger generations, it is important that it is updated with their current needs. Frequent updating and reviewing could be a great start to reflect on the newest advancements and trends in the agriculture industry. The school and the Department should provide opportunities and encourage teachers to engage in module writing and training workshops. Modules and other learning materials used in the classroom as instructional materials play a major role in guiding students' academic progress.

Agriculture organizations should be encouraged to participate in curriculum development to effectively share future trends and industry demands. These organizations can provide valuable inputs to ensure that the newest agricultural technologies and practices will be included in the curriculum.

Figure 7. Teacher participation in module development.

4. Promotion of Agricultural Careers and Opportunities

During the teaching-learning process, teachers should introduce to students the variety of job options in agriculture. Teachers can facilitate small career fairs, invite lecturers, and farm exposure as an initial introduction to the opportunities in the agriculture industry. Moreover, agriculture career talks from experts will elevate students' understanding of the importance and opportunities to venture into agriculture

(Caneda and Lantican, 2021). Another way is to encourage students to join in variety of contests to deeply motivate them to engage in agriculture.

Figure 8. Engagement in various contests and competitions related to agriculture.

The Local Government Unit (LGU) should launch various awareness campaigns and initiatives that highlight agriculture as a fulfilling and sustaining career option. These provide students with an additional drive to venture into the course. Offer recognition for groups and individuals who succeeded in the field of agriculture should also be done. The “Natatanging Guro Award” and “The Natatanging Anak ng Gumaca”, both initiated and regularly held by the municipal government should also be extended to “Natatanging Magsasaka” or “Anak ng Agrikultura”. This could lead to increased recognition in agriculture which will lead to increased recognition among students in Gumaca, Quezon.

Another initiative is the provision of scholarships and internships to students pursuing agricultural education. An example is the scholarship offered by the Philippine Coconut Authority (PCA). Students can avail free full tuition subsidy as long as their parents are registered coconut farmers. However, there is insufficient advertisement for the program. This could be strengthened if they conduct career guidance and seminars with the parents, teachers, and students to have a clear understanding of the program.

5. Intensification of Community and Industry Partnerships

The school and the teacher should ensure strong partnerships with other community associations, government groups, and agricultural enterprises in the municipality. Through this partnership, students can gain practical experience, guidance, and a deeper understanding pertaining to the significant role that agriculture plays in our society.

Figure 9. Partnership with community training and workshops.

The municipal government should consider giving rewards or recognition to agricultural businesses and organizations that facilitate partnerships with schools. Show strong support for policies that encourage partnerships in order to improve the quality of education. By doing so, agricultural organizations can have a significant impact on the development of the upcoming generation of agricultural professionals.

6. Utilization of Technology and Innovation

Initiates and sustains the use of technology in classroom teaching-learning. Students who are tech-savvy may be encouraged to engage in agricultural education.

This makes agricultural education more interesting and relevant to them if technology is incorporated (Robinson & Zajicek, 2015).

Figure 10. Gulayan sa Paaralan Website is utilized in teaching topics in agriculture.

Consider investing in the technology infrastructure of schools, more specifically in remote regions. This will ensure that students, regardless of their location, have access to the newest equipment and materials. The Department and the LGU should also consider donating technology to classrooms including free training on how to use it in teaching-learning. Interactive and engaging educational software and applications, such as the use of drones and satellite imaging, the use of AI for crop monitoring and management, hydroponics and aeroponics, are some examples of technology that can be offered to classroom.

7. Intensification of School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP)

The Department of Education (DepEd) implemented the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) under various policy issuances such as DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2017 (pre-pandemic) and DepEd Order No.22, s. 2020 (pandemic). SBFP is the flagship program of the Department of Education which aims to address hunger and

malnutrition among students in elementary and secondary public schools. This program is specially designed for students who need nutritional support (DepEd, 2023).

Gumaca National High School has continuously implemented SBFP since the day it was mandated by the Department. The SBFP, hand-in-hand with the Gulayan sa Paaralan Program (GPP), aims to improve the nutritional status of students who were evaluated as severely wasted and wasted based on the malnutrition classification. The operation and maintenance of GPP, aside from utilizing it as a platform for teaching-learning, support the full implementation of the SPFP. Making the students involved in the program, as part of taking Agri-Fishery as their specialization course, encourages them to increase accountability and awareness regarding the importance of proper nutrition in ensuring one's physical and mental health. The SBFP indirectly influences students' interest in choosing Agri-Fishery as their course of specialization. Through active participation, students deeply understand the essence of producing fresh and healthy vegetables for sustenance and nutrition. Seeing the beneficial effects of agriculture through GPP and SBFP, students develop a greater appreciation for the course. This may lead to an increased interest and motivation in pursuing agriculture in their higher years.

Figure 11. Harvested vegetables were utilized for School-Based Feeding Program.

8. Implementation of Permaculture in School

The school should also consider engaging in Permaculture. This strategy will help give students a deeper engagement in agriculture because this practice offers a holistic and hands-on approach to learning which contributes to sustainable and environmental conservation. Through permaculture, students will be aware of their duties and responsibilities in the attainment of Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), specifically ecological stewardship and sustainable living. With this practice, students will view agriculture as not just a subject to study, but an attractive and rewarding field as well.

As a design philosophy, permaculture, which is aimed at creating sustainable and self-sufficient human habitats, has gained popularity and proven effectiveness in some of the documented farms in the Philippines engaged in permaculture which

includes “Olaussen Permaculture Park at Layog Country Farm located in Tadian, Mountain Province, the “Cabiokid Foundation Inc.” situated in Cabiao, Nueva Ecija, the “Kai Farm” found in Silang, Cavite, the “Aloha Natural Farm” located in Puerto Princesa, Palawan, the “Glinoga Organic Farm” based in Pitogo, Quezon (first 2 photos), and the “Habilin Farms” Ilayang Bukal in Tayabas, Quezon. (last 2 photos).

Figure 12. Permaculture implemented at the “Glinoga Organic Farm” based in Pitogo, Quezon (first 2 photos), and the “Habilin Farms” Ilayang Bukal in Tayabas, Quezon.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

SELF-MADE INTERVIEW QUESTIONNAIRE

Part 1. Demographic Profile (Students)

A. PERSONAL INFORMATION

Name (Optional): _____ Grade and Section: _____

Age: _____ Gender: Male Female Prefer not to say

Ethnic background: Tagalog Non-Tagalog

Place of Residence:

Town (within the urban barangays)

Barrio (far-flung areas)

Have you performed agriculture-related work? Yes No

Do you have any plans of taking agriculture as a course in college?

Yes. No Not sure

B. FAMILY BACKGROUND

Educational Attainment of Father

- No formal educ
- Elementary Graduate
- High School Graduate
- Vocational Grad
- College Grad
- No formal educ

Educational Attainment of Mother

- No formal educ
- Elementary Graduate
- High School Graduate
- Vocational Grad
- College Grad
- No formal educ

Reasons for Choosing Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization (tick one or more)

- My parents asked me to take agriculture as my TLE Specialization
- It is an important subject that a student should study
- It is an interesting subject

- Teacher is students' favorite
- It is a compulsory subject

Do you regard Agriculture as Important as Other TLE Specialization?

Yes No

Do you have relatives with agriculture-related work?

Yes No

Occupation of Father

- Unskilled/Unemployed
- Skilled
- Education
- Government
- Business/Managers
- Professionals

Occupation of Mother

- Unskilled/Unemployed
- Skilled
- Education
- Government
- Business/Managers
- Professionals

Part 2. Perception of Students Towards Agriculture Specialization in Gumaca NHS

	STATEMENTS	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)
1	Agriculture specialization provides me with valuable hands-on experience with practical applications and relevant to the real world scenario				
2	The topics, learning tasks, and activities included in the current curriculum guide are aligned with my expectations, interests and career aspirations.				
3	I believe that agriculture education is given enough emphasis or importance in school and by the organization as a whole				
4	I believe that the skills and knowledge I acquire through agriculture education will be beneficial in my future endeavors.				
5	Growing up with relatives who work in the agricultural sector has inspired me to consider Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization				
6	My family's history of involvement in agriculture positively influences my interest in pursuing Agri-Fishery as my choice of TLE Specialization				
7	There is a high level of visibility and recognition of agriculture education in society and its given value and importance.				
8	Taking Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization increases popularity in school				
9	Choosing Agri-Fishery as TLE Specialization provides me with a high level of integrity				
10	I feel encouraged from pursuing agriculture because I believe there are lots of career opportunities in this field.				